

ENVIRONMENTAL RESISTANCE OF FLAX/BIO-BASED EPOXY AND FLAX/POLYURETHANE COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, many car manufacturers such as Audi, BMW and Ford have developed natural fibre composites components. The driver behind developing interior parts with natural fibres as reinforcements is to save weight without compromising mechanical properties, with the additional benefit of moving towards a more sustainable part production. Current biocomposites are based on the application of short, non-woven natural fibres. However, bonding hydrophilic natural fibres to a hydrophobic polymeric matrix can sometimes lead to a relatively poor interface, mostly because of the different polarities of the two components. In addition, natural fibre composites are highly sensitive to water absorption. The aim of this study was to compare the physical properties two biocomposites: (1) a flax/bio-based epoxy and (2) a flax/polyurethane. In fact, polyurethane is synthesized by polyaddition of an isocyanate and a polyol, an alcohol containing several hydroxyl groups. On the other hand, flax fibres are mainly composed of cellulose, a natural polymer that presents multiple hydroxyl groups. A crosslinking reaction between the polyurethane matrix and the cellulose in the fibres could increase the interface strength. Both materials were manufactured using a resin transfer moulding (RTM) process in order to maximize the fibre volume fraction and were reinforced with the same flax woven fabric. Post-cured composite samples were aged at 90%RH and 30°C. The results showed that both composites followed a Fickian diffusion behaviour and that flax/polyurethane composites were less sensitive to moisture ageing than flax/bio-epoxy composite. The chemical bonds between the hydroxyl groups of the fibres and the isocyanate lead to a stronger interface which improved the mechanical properties as compared to the flax/bio-epoxy composites. When exposed to moisture, the flax/polyurethane composite have more stable mechanical performances, especially the short beam strength, the compressive strength and the compressive modulus.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, flax fibres have been the subject of a significant amount of research regarding their potential for the development of bio-composites due to their specific properties, their price, their health advantages, such as the emission of VOC when machined, and their recyclability [1, 2]. Other properties, such as low wear on tools and good acoustic properties are also mentioned as benefits of natural fibres [1-5]. Approximately 315,000 tonnes of natural fibres were used as composite reinforcement in 2010, which accounted for 13% of the total reinforcement materials (glass, carbon and natural fibres) [6]. It is forecasted that about 830,000 tonnes of natural fibres will be incorporated in composite materials by 2020 [7]. Compared to glass fibres, flax fibres have similar specific properties and are available at a lower price [8, 9]. The automotive industry is probably the one that

uses the largest quantity of natural fibres. Most of the technologies are based on the application of the natural fibres as a non-woven material [1].

If natural fibres seem to be a particularly promising reinforcement, they also have disadvantages that need to be overcome before considering them for structural components: (1) the quality of natural fibres is not homogenous due to the variability of the conditions in which they are grown; (2) natural fibres start degrading at a temperature of about 200°C, a temperature at which most thermoplastics are processed; (3) natural fibres are hydrophilic and are therefore difficult to bond with an hydrophobic polymeric matrix; and (4) natural fibres absorb more moisture than synthetic fibres.

Several studies have shown that the mechanical properties of natural fibres composites are strongly affected by moisture absorption [2, 3, 10-23], but for now there is no clear understanding of the exact combination of water absorption mechanisms. A strong bond between fibres and matrix will maximize the mechanical performance of the composite as well as preventing the infiltration of water at the interface [19, 24]. Flax fibre cells are made of several walls, one primary and 3 secondary walls, that are composed of cellulose microfibrils ($\approx 70\%$) held together by hemicellulose ($\approx 15\%$) [2, 25]. Both these constituents have a high number of hydroxyl (O-H) group in their chemical structure which leads to a high polarity. Because bonding hydrophilic natural fibres to a hydrophobic polymeric matrix can lead to a relatively poor interface, it could be beneficial to use the flax hydroxyl groups in the polymerisation reaction to create a covalent bond between the fibres and the matrix. Polyurethane resins are a good candidate as they react with the N-H group of the urethane, present in the isocyanate pre-polymer, and with the hydroxyl groups of a polyol monomer.

This study is aimed at comparing two flax fibre reinforced composites using a bio-based epoxy resin and a polyurethane resin as matrices. As one of the goals of using natural fibres is to manufacture a material made of sustainable resources, the bio-based epoxy resin is a relevant choice to maximize the natural content of the composite. This paper focuses on two main issues: the interface adhesion between the flax fibres and the polymeric matrix and the moisture absorption of the composite after processing. Even though a very large quantity of work has been published on various natural fibres based bio-composites [3, 11-13, 16-19, 21-24, 26], it is not always easy or sometimes even possible to compare the materials used in different studies. In fact, the fibres type and architecture, the resin, the manufacturing process, the part dimensions, the ageing conditions and the tests performed often make a clear comparison impossible, even if common behaviours or phenomenon can be observed. An effort has been made in the present work to give an accurate comparison between two matrices which interact differently with the fibres. This could help to better understand the fibre/matrix interface and the water absorption mechanisms in bio-composites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The same flax woven fabric was used for both polyurethane (PU) and epoxy composites. The reinforcement was a twill 2x2 (ELINT58) with an areal weight of 245 g/m² that was provided by TEXONIC (Canada). A two-part SUPER SAP CLR/INS bio-based epoxy resin from Entropy Resin (Spain) was used in the Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process. 18% of the mixed resin weight is biobased (Biobased Carbon Content, ASTM D6866) and a mixed viscosity of 280cPs. The polyurethane was a two-part LOCTITE MAX 3 thermoset resin that was provided by HENKEL (Germany).

2.1 Composite Manufacturing using RTM

The resin transfer moulding aluminium tool is composed of three parts. On the bottom part, two cavities, located near the short sides of the mould, were machined so that the resin could impregnate the fibres along a line. A hole was drilled in each cavity to connect the inlet and the outlet tubing. The cavity dimensions are 208 mm x 163 mm x 5 mm (Fig. 1a)). The long edges of the reinforcement were sealed using tacky tape to avoid race tracking. A spacer of the desired thickness (in this case 5.00 mm) is placed between the bottom and the top part of the mould. An optimum seal is achieved by using two silicone O-rings and vacuum grease. The seal was tested each time and was able to maintain -29 in.Hg

for 5 minutes. Fourteen layers of the flax woven fabric were cut to dimensions (200 mm x 160 mm), before being stacked and dried under a vacuum bag at 140°C for 8h. All the reinforcements came from the same roll. The fibres were then placed in the mould treated with a Zivax Envirosshield release agent (Figure 1b)).

Figure 1: RTM Tool – a) Bottom Part of the Mould; b) Bottom Part, Spacer and Flax Fibre

The mould was closed using a small hydraulic press equipped with heating platens (Figure 2). A clamping force of 5 metric tons was applied. Prior to the injection, the tool temperature was brought to 50°C and 25°C for the epoxy and the polyurethane respectively. The outlet was connected to a resin trap and a vacuum pump. Afterward, the resin was mixed, degassed for 4 minutes at -28 In.Hg and placed in a pressure tank connected to the inlet of the mould. Using compressed air, the injection pressure was gradually applied for 1 min. For the epoxy resin, an injection pressure of 3.45 bars was used and the remaining voids were collapsed by increasing the pressure to 4.8 bars once the infusion was finished. The polyurethane resin was injected at 4.8 bars and was not increased after the infusion. At 50°C, the polyurethane viscosity increased from 100cPs to 200cPs in 8 minutes, whereas in the case of the bio-epoxy the viscosity stayed at 280 cPs during the entire process. When using a resin infusion process, the viscosity is a key parameter for choosing the suitable resin. It becomes even more important when using natural fibres and high fibre volume fraction (V_f), i.e. above 40% V_f . When the fibres were completely impregnated and the flow of resin coming out of the mould was stabilized, the out tubing was clamped and unclamped 2-3 times in order to generate a brief pressure gradient to remove the remaining air bubbles. In the case of the epoxy, the tool was then heated to 50°C for six hours. For the polyurethane, the mould temperature was held at 50°C for five hours. The mould was cooled to room temperature before demoulding the biocomposites panels. Six polyurethane and twelve epoxy composites panels were made. Excellent panel quality was obtained thanks to the RTM process. All panels had a smooth surface finish, a homogenous thickness and no visible macrovoids. The average fibre volume fraction was 42.4% and 38.9% for the epoxy and polyurethane panels respectively. It was calculated using the mass of the reinforcement, the mass of the final part and the density of the fibres and the resins.

Figure 2: Composite Manufacturing - Resin Transfer Moulding Process

2.2 Short Beam Shear and Shear Loading Compression Tests

There is no commonly used test to characterize the fibre/matrix interface in a cured composite laminate [27]. Therefore, two different tests were selected to measure the mechanical properties that are closely related and sensitive to the fibre/matrix adhesion. Short beam shear tests (ASTM D2344) were performed to measure the interlaminar shear strength, a property directly affected by the bond quality between the fibres and the matrix. Shear-Loading Compression tests (ASTM D3410) were also performed. In fact, the compressive strength of a laminate containing interlaminar damages is likely to be degraded because individual plies are free to exhibit local instabilities [27]. Therefore, the evolution of the compression properties during ageing should be a good indicator of the effects of moisture on the interface and the interlaminar strength of the composite. Both tests were performed on a 10kN INSTRON 3300 dual column universal testing system with fixtures made by Wyoming Test Fixtures. The composite panels were machined to the proper dimensions and tolerances using a BRIDGEPORT Vertical 2-axis milling machine with a diamond coated carbide end mill. Six flax/polyurethane and twelve flax/bio-epoxy panels were machined. In each panels, 7 short beam shear test coupons and 7 shear loading compression coupons were machined. The short beam shear coupons dimensions were 31.8 mm x 10.6 mm and the shear load compression coupons were 145 mm x 10 mm. No water or cutting fluid was used in order to avoid wetting the samples before ageing.

2.3 Water Absorption and Gravimetric Analysis

All the tests coupons were stored in sealed bags with desiccant immediately after manufacturing and machining. No weight reduction was observed when drying the first batch of coupons under vacuum at 40°C for 24h. Therefore, the sealed bags with desiccant method was considered sufficient to dry the test coupons before ageing. All the samples were weighted on a SARTORIUS entris244-1s scale with a precision of 1 mg. The water absorption characteristics of the composites were evaluated by the relative weight gain.

The machined samples were conditioned at 30°C and 90%RH in a CONVIRON environmental chamber. The ageing conditions were monitored using the environmental chamber sensors. In most studies [11, 16, 17, 26, 28, 29], Fick's second law of diffusion is used to model the global water absorption behaviour of the composite and gives accurate results. However, it should be noted that this model is not representative of the various phenomenon happening in a two-phase material [12]. The times at which the samples were tested were therefore determined according the square root of time. For the short beam shear and the shear load compression tests, 7 coupons were cut from the same panel and conditioned for the following periods of time: 6h, 23h, 91h, 336h and 720h. Each period of time corresponds to 2 flax/bio-epoxy panels and 1 flax/polyurethane panel. The test coupons were weighted before conditioning and within the 5 minutes following their conditioning. They were then placed in a sealed bag to limit contact with the ambient air and removed just before their mechanical testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water Absorption of the Laminates

Figure 3 shows the percentage of water absorbed for the samples after 90% RH ageing at 30°C, as a function of square root of ageing time. The samples have not reach saturation yet but follow a linear trend, which is typical of a Fickian diffusion behaviour. In fact, in the case of a one-dimensional approach of Fick's law, the water uptake increases linearly with the square root of time, and then gradually slows until an equilibrium plateau is reached, typically after a month for flax composite exposed to 90% RH [16]. In Figure 3, a linear regression was done for the first part of the curve, i.e. before the equilibrium plateau. After 720h of ageing, the bio-epoxy samples were saturated and the polyurethane samples were reaching equilibrium. The polyurethane composites absorb moisture at a much slower rate than the epoxy composites. As the polyurethane and the epoxy resin can only absorb a very small amount of water, typically around 1% or less, it is the hydrophilic fibres that are mainly responsible for the water absorption of the composite [10, 16]. A smaller water absorption rate indicates that the fibres/matrix interaction is different [28, 30, 31]. This can be explained by the formation of bonds between the urethane pre-polymer and the hydroxyl group of the flax fibres. A reduction in the available hydroxyl groups would lead to a reduction in the moisture absorption rate.

Figure 3: Water uptake of flax fibre reinforced composites after 90% RH ageing at 30°C

3.2 Mechanical Properties

The influence of humidity on the mechanical behaviour during the short beam shear tests is shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Bio-Epoxy panels are labelled A, B, C, D and E. Polyurethane panels were labelled α , β , γ , δ and ϵ . Each panel corresponds to one ageing time. Before ageing, both epoxy and polyurethane composites failed in a combination of interlaminar shear and tension failure modes (Figure 7a)), allowing the determination of the apparent short beam strength of the material (Figure 6). After 23h of ageing, the flax/bio-epoxy samples no longer failed, they deformed plastically at a much lower load than initially (Figure 7b)). No apparent short beam strength could be calculated for the flax/epoxy composite after 23h of ageing. The presence of water in the fibres increased the mobility between the microfibrils and resulted in a plasticizing effect [16, 32]. With water acting as a plasticizer, the internal bonds between microfibrils are softened, thus weakening the composite reinforcement and modifying its behaviour. In addition, the bio-epoxy resin has a relatively low glass

transition temperature (T_g , 48.3°C according to the manufacturer) that could have been affected by the hygrothermal ageing [33]. If the composite glass transition temperature (T_g) went below room temperature after 91h of ageing, this could be an explanation of the changes in the composite behaviour. For the flax/polyurethane composites, the absorbed water still has a plasticizing effect, even if the weight gain after one month is less important for the flax/polyurethane composite, i.e. 9.7% and 7.6% for the epoxy and the polyurethane respectively. Both composites have reached saturation after one month of ageing.

As can be seen in Figure 6, the absorbed water had a significant impact on the short beam strength of the flax/bio-epoxy composite; it drops by 17.6% in 23h and cannot be measured afterward as the material started to deform plastically. On the other hand, there is a slight increase in the short beam strength of the flax/polyurethane samples at the beginning of the ageing. The absorbed moisture does not affect the fibres and the interface bonds in the polyurethane composite the same way it does in the bio-epoxy composite.

Figure 4: Short Beam Shear Tests after 90% RH ageing at 30°C - Flax/Bio-Epoxy
 Failure Mode: S/T Interlaminar Shear/Tension ; ID Inelastic Deformation

Figure 5: Short Beam Shear Tests after 90% RH ageing at 30°C - Flax/Polyurethane
Failure Mode: S/T Interlaminar Shear/Tension ; ID/S Inelastic Deformation/Interlaminar Shear

Figure 6: Evolution of the Short Beam Strength of Flax/Bio-Epoxy and Flax/Polyurethane Composites

Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the influence of humidity on the mechanical behaviour during the shear loading compression tests. At the beginning of the conditioning, all the samples failed according to a through-thickness failure mode in the gauge section (Figure 7c)). In the case of the bio-epoxy matrix, the plasticizing effect of water affected the material rapidly and can be noticed after 23h of hygrothermal ageing. After 91h of conditioning, the failure mode of the bio-epoxy samples change to brooming (Figure 7d)), i.e. the sample expand perpendicularly to the loading axe. After 720h, both the ultimate compressive strength and the compressive modulus of elasticity of the bio-epoxy composites were reduced by 70.3% and 76.4% respectively (Figure 10). According to the bio-epoxy manufacturer, the ultimate compressive strength of the neat resin is 85.4 MPa (ASTM D695), which is higher than the compressive strength of the flax/bio-epoxy composite after 91h. This can either suggest that the composite T_g is lower than the room temperature or that the fibres and the interface are drastically weakened by the water and cannot be loaded anymore.

After 336h, the compressive modulus and the compressive strength of the flax/polyurethane samples are reduced by 52.7% and 35.5% respectively. The polyurethane are less affected by moisture and break through the thickness in a consistent manner, showing that the fibre/matrix interface is stronger because of the covalent bonds created between the hydroxyl groups of the cellulosic fibres and the polyurethane matrix.

Figure 7: Typical Fracture Mode of Flax Composites

- a) Interlaminar Shear/Tension (flax/PU, 23h) b) Inelastic Deformation (flax/bio-epoxy, 336h)
c) Through the thickness (flax/PU, 23h) d) Brooming (flax/bio-epoxy, 91h)

Figure 8: Shear Loading Compression Tests after 90% RH ageing at 30°C - Flax/Bio-Epoxy
 Failure Mode: H Through-the-Thickness ; B Brooming

Figure 9: Shear Loading Compression Tests after 90% RH ageing at 30°C - Flax/Polyurethane
 Failure Mode: H Through-the-Thickness ; H/B Through-the-Thickness then Brooming

Figure 10: Evolution of the Compressive Strength of Bio-Epoxy and Polyurethane Composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed at investigating the influence of hygrothermal ageing on the fibre/matrix interface and the mechanical properties of composites laminates reinforced by a woven flax fabric. A bio-based epoxy and a thermoset polyurethane resin were used to manufacture composite panels using a resin transfer moulding process. From this work, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Moisture absorption follows a Fickian diffusion behaviour for both composites. Polyurethane absorb less moisture and at a slower rate. The chemical bonding between the hydroxyl groups of the cellulosic fibres and the urethane pre-polymer results in a reduction of the available hydroxyl groups. This directly influence the way the composite fibres interact with water and absorb moisture.
- The short beam shear failure of the flax/bio-epoxy change from an interlaminar shear/tension mode to inelastic deformation mode with the absorption of moisture. This is caused by the plasticizing effect of the absorbed water. Water also has a plasticizing effect on the polyurethane composites but it does not change their failure mode.
- The shear loading compression tests showed the same plasticizing effects of water, with a change of the failure mode happening after 23h of ageing for the bio-epoxy matrix. Overall, the mechanical performances of the polyurethane composites are less affected by moisture absorption than those of the bio-epoxy composites. As the two tests performed are very sensitive to the fibre/matrix bonding, this confirms that the adhesion between the fibres and the matrix is stronger in the case of the polyurethane matrix.

The results analysis showed that for cellulosic fibres reinforced composites, the use of polyurethane resin is highly beneficial for the environmental stability, the durability and the moisture resistance of the material. It also shows that the nature of the fibre/matrix interface plays a key role in the moisture absorption mechanisms.

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